

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Review on designing a comprehensive macroeconomic modeling strategy for antimicrobial resistance

Poojitha Gone, Raju Darla * and Sai Priya K

Joginpalli B R Pharmacy College, Yenkapalli, Moinabad, Rangareddy-500075, Telangana, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(01), 705–716

Publication history: Received on 21 September 2022; revised on 25 October 2022; accepted on 27 October 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.1.1096>

Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a dominant and growing global health crisis that led to 1.27 million deaths in 2019. Given the broad use of antimicrobials in agriculture and farming and industrial operations in addition to healthcare and a range of factors affecting AMR, including climate variability, demographic trends, and plastic and essence pollution, an frugality-wide approach is essential to assess its macroeconomic counter accusations. This study summarizes the being literature on the linked factors driving AMR and reviews the factors that have been considered in being macroeconomic studies. We present three fabrics to conceptualize the frugality-wide use of antimicrobials, the epidemiology of AMR, and how AMR affects the economy in a stylized frugality bedded within a more expansive system. We propose how the AMR impacts could be counterplotted onto profitable variables, bandy the significance of these shocks, and outline how AMR elaboration scripts could be designed, particularly with reference to climate change, demographic trends, and associated socioeconomic changes. We also bandy how modeling studies could be bettered to increase their mileage to policymakers and increase similarity across studies. We conclude with the major policy counter accusations arising from the study which emphasizes an frugality-wide one- health approach to address AMR; regulation of the antimicrobial force chain and incentivizing inventions; global cooperation to address AMR, and easing misgivings for policymaking via spanning up the surveillance of AMR, encouraging exploration collaboration and enabling access to data on AMR and antimicrobial consumption.

Keywords: Antimicrobial resistance; COVID-19; World Health Organization (WHO); United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP); Macro economy

1. Introduction

1.1. Economic importance of microorganisms

Microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, contagions, algae, and protozoa, have played a vital role in the survival and evolution of creatures. One of the most important functions of microorganisms is recovering organic and inorganic matter through their interactions in the carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur cycles via which they contribute to maintaining the stability of the biosphere. Microorganisms are also the basic source of nutrients in numerous food chains. The reactions of microorganisms on organic and inorganic matter have been utilized in agricultural farming and artificial operations (e.g., fermentation and conflation of proteins and enzymes). Still, microorganisms also have a range of undesirable consequences on the survival of creatures, including microbial diseases. The literal pestilences similar as the “Black Death” and the ongoing COVID- 19 pandemic exemplify the negative counter accusations of microorganisms on humans. With the advancement of scientific technology, methodologies to harness the positive implications and reduce the negative impacts of microorganisms have been developed. The discovery and bulk production of antimicrobial drug and

* Corresponding author: Raju Darla

Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry; Joginpalli B R Pharmacy College, Yenkapalli, Moinabad, Rangareddy- 500075. Telangana, India.

chemicals has been an effective response to constrain the undesirable counter accusations of microorganisms. The discovery of antimicrobial medicine, similar as penicillin and sulfonamides in the early 1900s, revolutionized the treatment of microbial infections and has been vital to medical procedures, similar as cesarean sections, chemotherapy, organ transplants, and surgeries. Presently, antimicrobials are used in agriculture and farming for remedial, metaphylaxis, and prophylaxis purposes and growth creation. In industrial applications, antimicrobials are used to control the ability of microorganisms where physical processes (similar as irradiation or heat) are ineffective or impractical.

1.2. AMR: Origins and evolution

Conforming to grueling and changing surroundings or circumstances is a abecedarian motorist of the evolution of all living beings, which is also applicable to microorganisms. Consequently, developing resistance to antimicrobials is an element of the natural evolution of microorganisms. While some microorganisms are intrinsically resistant to antimicrobials, there are two main ways a non-intrinsically resistant microorganism acquires resistance: inheritable mutations within the cell to its own chromosomal DNA and accession of genetic material from a resistant cell via metamorphosis, transduction, or conjugation. Antimicrobials often target destroying a microorganism or suppressing its growth by either disruption the cell membrane, inhibiting cell wall conflation, inhibiting protein conflation, inhibiting nucleic acid (DNA or RNA) conflation, or inhibiting metabolism¹. While intrinsically resistant microorganisms would either have an impermeable cell membrane acquired resistance could lead to producing enzymes that kill antimicrobials, pumping antimicrobials out of the cells, or modifying the target of antimicrobials. When antimicrobials are used to exclude the susceptible and non-resistant strains to the antimicrobials, the survival advantage for the resistant strains increases. Overuse, abuse and underuse of antimicrobials for numerous applications, including remedial uses, and nonstop exposure of antimicrobials in the nature (similar as in healthcare settings, wastewater treatment installations, and the erected terrain) further increase the selective pressure and accelerate the resistant acquisition rates among microorganisms. With the exposure to a broader array of antimicrobials, some microorganisms have developed resistance not only to a single antimicrobial targeting them but to multiple antimicrobials. The microorganisms are appertained to as “superbugs”².

1.3. Factors driving AMR

Insufficient consumption of antimicrobials and selective pressure wielded by similar consumption is the uncontested and immediate factor driving AMR. A vast body of literature explores how antimicrobial consumption in different sectors, particularly healthcare and husbandry (including crops, beast, and aquaculture), has exacerbated AMR³. In the healthcare sector, a wide range of literature analyzes the insufficient antimicrobial consumption among individualities, within primary care settings. The literature also frequently focuses on different infections and/ or antimicrobial-pathogen combinations and illustrates possible interventions to reduce lack of diagnosis, prescription and consumption. However, as Llor and Bjerrum⁴ suggest, health standards and practices, socio cultural characteristics (similar as stations, beliefs, comprehensions, etc.), and socioeconomic background (similar as the healthcare financing structure, profitable impulses handed by the medicinal assiduity, and income distribution) of colorful countries impact the geste of patients and healthcare interpreters when consuming antimicrobials. To understand the underpinning factors driving antimicrobial consumption in the healthcare sector, the World Health Organization (WHO) (2015) recommends the use of the Knowledge- station- Practice (KAP) framework⁵. Consequently, a large body of regional, public, and sub-national studies explores the role of socio cultural and socioeconomic factors above in driving antimicrobial opinion, tradition, and consumption practices in different corridor of the world. Demography is another pivotal factor frequently highlighted in KAP studies when explaining the variation of antimicrobial consumption across countries. There's also a wide range of studies assessing the demographic characteristics of cases suffering from colorful infections affected by AMR and the part of demographic factors in the consumption of antimicrobials⁶⁻¹¹. Some of the common demographic factors considered in these studies are age, gender, connubial status, educational position, income, occupation, and place of hearthstone. Although limited, existing time- series studies have also explored the implications of broader demographic trends similar as changes in population growth and viscosity^{12, 13}, population aging^{14, 15}, and migration¹⁶⁻¹⁹. Specially, the studies on population aging point out a two way relationship with AMR. As the vulnerability to infections increases and with multi morbidity (the co-occurrence of multiple chronic conditions), the senior populations require more antimicrobial drug. Consequently, consuming more antimicrobials by the senior population increase the picky pressure for microorganisms and aggravates AMR. Poly pharmacy, or the reliance on multiple antimicrobials to treat colorful conditions and conditions among senior people, enables resistance acquisition among colorful microorganisms and gives rise to superbugs. Exacerbating AMR, in turn, reduces the effectiveness of being drug and disproportionately affects the aging population. An ecological perspective on AMR recognizes the interactions among pathogens and commensal microorganisms and how similar relations would strengthen the accession, retention, and increase of AMR²⁰⁻²². The presence of AMR genes in humans and creatures, especially in remote areas of the world, indeed in the absence of sustained exposure to antimicrobials²³. They emphasize the part of environmental impurity

and environmental ecosystems (similar as gutters) in transmitting AMR genes. Precluding both the natural (similar as air, soil, and aqueducts) and erected terrain (similar as sanitation structure) from getting reservoirs of antimicrobial genes is therefore pivotal to preventing the spread of AMR²⁴⁻²⁶. The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) (2017) discusses the part of not only antimicrobial medicine but also other antimicrobial chemicals, such as biocides. An arising body of substantiation demonstrates how plastic pollution, particularly microplastics in marine ecosystems, increases the face area for the growth of pathogens and thereby aggravates AMR²⁷⁻²⁹. A analogous beachfront of studies discusses the role of soil pollution convinced by heavy essence (particularly mercury, cadmium, bobby, and zinc) in co-selection and thereby exacerbating AMR^{30,31}. UNEP (2022) highlights the importance of effectively managing effluent and waste from medicinal diligence, healthcare installations, crops, beast, fish processing diligence, and other industries considerably using antimicrobials. With the frequency of antimicrobial genes in the terrain, the movement of humans and live creatures, especially across borders, enables the global spread of AMR.

In a recent review, found that out of, 30,060 resistant isolates estimated, the most common origin of resistant genes was Asia, counting for 36 percent of the total isolated genes³². High income countries encyclopedically are more likely to be recipients of AMR genes. Plaza- Rodriguez present substantiation for AMR genes in migratory catcalls³³, and Arnold emphasize the part of submarine and terrestrial wildlife trade and transfer in the spread of AMR genes³⁴. Collignon also observe the role of governance in explaining the diversity of AMR across countries³⁵. These findings point to the importance of empowering health systems and policies worldwide and how AMR has come a 'global wicked problem' that requires collaborative action. Climate variability has lately garnered attention as another critical medium affecting AMR. Existing studies have set up substantiation of rising AMR amidst increasing average temperatures. Rodriguez-Verdugo illustrate that the adding temperature could affect the response of pathogens to antimicrobials at three primary situations physiological, inheritable, and community levels³⁶. Gudipati argue that some of the factors contributing to climate change, similar as land use changes via deforestation and ferocious agricultural practices, have exacerbated AMR from disruptions to beast territories. In addition to the direct implications on AMR, climate variability could also indirectly affect AMR through its impacts on the prevalence of infections and the performing demand for antimicrobial consumption³⁷. Cavicchioli explain how host- pathogen relations change amidst climate variability, which could prompt water, air, food, and vector- borne conditions to spread briskly. Addressing climate change is also likely to be pivotal for taming AMR³⁸.

1.4. Implications of AMR: Current understanding

Utmost being studies have emphasized the AMR implications on human, beast, and environmental (mostly plant) health. The actuality of AMR among pathogens was known indeed before the discovery of antimicrobial medicine, and the development of resistance was expected indeed during the early stages of antimicrobial medicine development. Since the 1950s, when utmost of moment's antimicrobial drugs were developed, the pharmaceutical industry has continued to learn about pathogens' biochemical reactions and resistance mechanisms and improved the drug to repel them. Still, with the increase in resistance, the antimicrobial medicine administration regulations bear using the new antimicrobial medicine sparingly this reduces the exposure of the antimicrobial drug to pathogens or microorganisms in general. Accordingly, this reduces the opportunity for the pharmaceutical assiduity to recover the underlying significant investment costs in antimicrobial medicine product by dealing the drug widely and for a longer period of time.

Consequently, no new classes of antimicrobial drug have been discovered since the 1980s³⁹⁻⁴⁰. About 43 traditional antimicrobial medicines are currently in the clinical development stage, and 292 are in the pre-clinical development stage. Of these, only 26 and 60, independently, concentrate on the precedence pathogens⁴¹ (some of which are multidrug-resistant) (WHO 2022). WHO recognizes AMR as one of the top ten global public health pitfalls. The declining efficacy of antimicrobial medicines is leading to numerous challenges. Infections are taking longer to heal and are costlier to treat. Some infections cannot be treated with existing antimicrobial drug, vulnerability to infections and the threat of death from infections are adding, Infections formerly canceled in one part of the world are re-emerging or arising in a different part of the world, New infections are arising, and The effectiveness of medical procedures is reduced. Increasing mortality and morbidity from infections is the main pathway through which AMR affects humans. In 2014, KPMG and RAND Europe estimated that, 700, 000 deaths were attributable to AMR related to HIV, Malaria, Tuberculosis, and three precedence pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*), and that the deaths could reach 10 million per annum by 2050⁴².

Cecchini illustrated that the likelihood of dying from an infection could increase three fold in G7 countries if the infection doesn't respond to antimicrobial drug⁴³. In 2017, the Centre for Disease Control (2019) estimated that two million infections were attributable to AMR in the United States alone, leading to at least 23000 deaths. The European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (2017) estimated 25,000 AMR- attributable deaths in Europe in the same year. The rearmost global estimate on AMR- attributable deaths is handed in the Global Burden of Bacterial Antimicrobial

Resistance study (GRAM) for 2019, released in 2022. According to that report, 1.27 million lives lost in 2019 have been attributed to 23 pathogens resistant to being antimicrobial drug. A one- health frame recognizes mortal, beast, and factory(environmental) health as interconnected components when achieving optimal planetary health. Within a one-health frame, direct and circular costs of AMR could be identified. The direct costs of AMR encompass out of- fund expenditures(from cases or growers), treatment costs borne by the health services, treatment costs for cases for long-term complications, costs of decontamination in the case of the terrain, surveillance of AMR, training for healthcare and other applicable professionals, and legal and insurance costs. The circular costs include occasion costs of, morbidity and mortality among the labor force, public healthcare expenditure, healthcare coffers, research and development costs, loss of productivity in the livestock sector, and fresh burden to consumers from reduced product. Feting AMR's direct and indirect costs within a one- health frame demonstrates the applicability of a frugality-wide response to AMR and how counteraccusations on one element of the triad could unmask over to other components. Alternatively, the burden of AMR could also be evaluated at multiple categories case, healthcare system, and the frugality or society ⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶. Health economic approaches have been extensively employed to assess the burden of AMR at the first two situations and the costs considered include sanitarium residency, use of drug, laboratory services and medical procedures, and human resource application. At the societal or economic level, the focus has been on the loss of productivity and healthcare expenditure. Covering HIV, Malaria, Tuberculosis, and three priority pathogens(*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*), as well as their goods on morbidity and mortality among workers and government expenditure on healthcare, KPMG(2014) and RAND Europe(2014) anticipate the accretive economic burden of AMR to reach\$ US 100 trillion by 2050. Using a analogous methodology, Ahmed ⁴⁷ (2017) estimate the burden of AMR to reach\$ US 85 trillion between2015 to 2050. OCEC (2018) estimates that in 33European countries alone, the direct periodic healthcare cost associated with AMR could be as high as\$ US3.5 billion. The World Bank(2017), considering implication son beast in addition to mortality and morbidity among humans due to AMR, estimates that under a low-AMR script, global periodic GDP losses could exceed\$ US 1 trillion after 2030 and reach\$ US 2 trillion by 2050. Under a high- AMR script, the monthly GDP losses could reach\$ US3.4 trillion by 2030 and\$ US6.1 trillion by 2050. WHO(2021b) also demonstrates the disproportionate burden of AMR on developing countries, and how an fresh28.3 million people could be pushed into poverty in these countries. Progress toward achieving at least seven Sustainable Development pretensions (SDGs) is directly affected, and about six fresh SDGs could be laterally affected by AMR. Thus, containing AMR is central to both sustainable profitable growth and development.

2. Economic implications of AMR

2.1. Modeling the economic implications of AMR: Current understanding

Early studies assessing the profitable counteraccusations of AMR extended the fundamental health profitable approaches, similar as cost minimization, cost- effectiveness, cost- benefit, or cost- mileage analyses, to estimate the fresh burden of infections affected by AMR. With the growing appreciation of the significance of AMR as a problem beyond infections, three main beaches of literature assessing the profitable counteraccusations of AMR can be linked in more recent studies. The first beachfront considers the patient burden of AMR due to mortality and morbidity arising from infections affected by AMR. The alternate beachfront assesses the healthcare system burden of AMR due to secondary infections in cases due to AMR and extended sanitarium care induced by infections affected by AMR. These studies substantially use retrogression analysis and significance tests. The third beachfront assesses the frugality-wide counteraccusations of AMR. These studies substantially use partial or computable generable equilibrium(CGE)models. One of the foremost attempts to apply an frugality-wide CGE model to AMR was to assess the counteraccusations of methicillin- resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*(MRSA) in Britain. The unrestricted- frugality model featured ten sectors, a representative establishment in each sector, a representative consumer, a bank, and a government. AMR has been introduced as a shock on labor force, sectoral productivity, and a cost to healthcare delivery. The simulations demonstrated the counteraccusations of AMR on macroeconomic summations similar as GDP, investment, savings, consumption, employment, and weal. The operation of the GLOBE model extended CGE modeling to the global frugality. The approach involved evolving antibiotic resistance as a function of tradition and calculating morbidity and mortality estimates due to pathogens developing resistance to the antibiotics. The study explored the counteraccusations on savings, trade, and exchange rates and estimated the implicit of interventions to reduce antibiotic consumption and optimize antibiotic prescriptions. The first methodical review of the profitable counteraccusations arising from the precedence pathogens and infections acquiring resistance to being antimicrobials against them was commissioned in 2014 by the Prime Minister of the United Kingdom. The review, chaired by Jim O'Neil and completed in 2016, included two profitable studies conducted by KPMG and RAND Europe in 2014. KPMG(2014) employed a partial general equilibrium model where total factor productivity(TFP) was modeled as a function of five factors macroeconomic stability, the openness of the frugality, quality of structure, the strength of public institutions, and human capital. The impacts on TFP were combined with the goods modeled on the labor force due to stoked mortality and morbidity related to AMR and capital- income rate to derive the counteraccusations on the global frugality. The study was also

supplemented with analysis of fiscal impacts at the indigenous position, expiring from public health expenditure spent on combating AMR. The CGE model used by RAND Europe (2014) had shocks on population growth — due to mortality — and labor effectiveness — due to morbidity impacts of AMR. Ahmed ⁴⁷ (2017) used the GLOBE- Dyn model, there cursive dynamic interpretation of the GLOBE model, to assess the global macroeconomic impacts of AMR due to the same precedence pathogens and infections covered in the AMR. Extending the KPMG and RAND Europe (2014) studies, the reduction in beast product and global restrictions on beast trade were considered. The World Bank (2017) has also estimated the AMR implications on both the labor force and beast under two AMR evolution scripts, although the details handed on the modeling approach are limited. OECD (2018) used the OECD Strategic Public Health Planning for AMR (SPHeP- AMR) model, a health profitable model, with an expansive focus on the elaboration of AMR and the epidemiology of the infections affected by AMR. The study also covered eight pathogens and considered the counteraccusations of AMR on medical procedures in addition to infections.

2.2. Modeling the economic implications of AMR: Limitations and challenges

While the being studies give precious estimates of the profitable burden of AMR, figure out several limitations that unborn studies should address⁴⁸. Designing dependable future AMR evolution scenarios is abecedarian to the modeling. Such efforts should consider the transmission dynamics of AMR within a one- health frame. Likewise, then on-direct connections between AMR and antimicrobial consumption need to be more understood. The existing studies also don't demonstrate the part of behavioral and social factors, similar as patient compliance with infection forestallment and antimicrobial treatment measures. They also emphasize obtaining country-specific estimates to capture the heterogeneity across colorful corridor of the world and increase transparency when reporting modeling methodologies and results. A major challenge in assessing the profitable implications of AMR lies in the lack of antimicrobial consumption and resistance data. There's no comprehensive accounting of the frugality-wide production of antimicrobials, particularly antimicrobial medicine. Even the stylish available data on antimicrobial medicine consumption, which comes from the Global Antibiotic Consumption and operation in Humans study by the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME), is likely to underrate factual antimicrobial medicine consumption because of the frequency of informal antimicrobial product, especially at household levels. Indeed though personal advanced quality data on antimicrobial deals are available with pharmaceutical companies and private realities that collect similar data, the data aren't affordable for utmost researchers. Although the trade data available from the United Nations Com trade database could be a useful source for identifying pharmaceutical deals across countries, disaggregating the data for antimicrobial classes remains a challenge. The vacuity of global grainy data on the use of antimicrobial chemicals in husbandry and industries is indeed lower than that for pharmaceuticals. Global surveillance of AMR by WHO only commenced in 2015, with the launch of the Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS). GLASS provides a standardized approach to collecting, assaying, interpreting, and participating data on AMR. Before that, only a sprinkle of high- income countries (including Europe and the United States) had national or indigenous expansive surveillance mechanisms. The possibility of conducting global panel studies on historical data is therefore limited. Indeed though the data on AMR rates in the food chain and terrain is even more limited than in healthcare, GLASS is anticipated to incorporate those sectors into surveillance gradually. The GRAM study provides the regional AMR rates for 88 medicine- pathogen combinations covering 23 pathogens and 12 infections in 2019. The study also provides a harmonious frame to collude the consumption of antimicrobial drug to infections, which was a challenge until the study was published.

3. An integrated framework for assessing the macroeconomic consequences of AMR

In the above sections, we have reviewed the existing literature modeling the economic implications of AMR and the areas where modeling can be improved. In this section, we discuss three critical issues for designing an integrated modeling exercise on AMR: (1) Modeling the epidemiology of AMR, (2) Designing AMR evolution scenarios, and (3) Modeling the macroeconomic implications of AMR. The following sections discuss how these issues could be addressed despite the existing challenges, especially regarding data.

3.1. Modeling the epidemiology of AMR

3.1.1. Role of antimicrobial consumption in aggravating AMR

The extensively cited frame for the epidemiology of AMR illustrates the role of antimicrobials in mortal consumption, husbandry (crops, beast, and monoculture), and industrial operations⁴⁹. It also outlines how antimicrobial consumption in homes, husbandry, and diligence could interact with environmental ecosystems and pollute the environment. We extend this frame to punctuate artificial operations of antimicrobials that are amenable to profitable modeling. Antimicrobials always reach the ecosystems through a profitable sector unless explicitly added. The husbandry sector consists of crops, monoculture and fisheries, beast and companion animals, and forestry and wildlife. Antimicrobials

(similar as Streptomycin, Oxytetracycline, Gentamicin, etc.) are used to help conditions in crops (substantially rice, wheat, cereals, vegetables, and fruits) and as an cumulative to fertilizers. Beast feed and monoculture use antimicrobials for remedial, metaphylaxis, and prophylaxis purposes, and growth promotion⁵⁰. The main artificial operations of antimicrobials are food product and packaging, cloth manufacturing, sanitizers, maquillages, coatings, complements, preservatives, and petroleum recovery (in the energy sector).

The paints, coatings, complements, and preservatives are then used in secondary operations in the manufacturing (similar as wood, paper, fabrics and cosmetics, plastics, and essence), energy, and services (similar as construction, transportation, and mileage) sectors, demonstrating the economy wide consumption of antimicrobials. Antimicrobial remainders from husbandry, diligence, and services pollute the ecosystems substantially through solid waste and backwaters. The exposure of antimicrobials to air via their artificial operations also increases the picky pressure. Relations among the forestry and wildlife with soil and water bodies grease resistance gene transfer and the discovery of new hosts. Human relations with the ecosystems and wildlife, substantially via recreational conditioning and agrarian and industrial operations, also enable resistance gene transfer.

3.1.2. Role of factors other than antimicrobial consumption in aggravating AMR

The extended frame for the epidemiology of AMR in antimicrobial consumption to be the sole motorist of AMR. While it's the dominant motorist, as banded in Section 1.3, other factors, similar as socioeconomic, socio cultural, demographic, and environmental factors, either directly affect AMR or indirectly affect AMR via antimicrobial consumption. In addition to antimicrobial consumption in healthcare, husbandry, and diligence, impurity of ecosystems with antimicrobials and other AMR promoters, global and public demographic trends, governance, health system adaptability to internal and external health pitfalls, climate variability, and openness to travel are important factors that contribute to AMR. As banded in Section 1.3, there is already substantiation for numerous of these factors. Still, there is a general lack of methodical studies exploring the part of governance, health system adaptability, and some aspects of demographic trends and climate variability. The ICRG frame is a helpful starting point for evaluating the counteraccusations of AMR's methodical risks. The International Country Risk Guide (ICRG) (The PRS Group 2012) considers 22 pointers across three primary groups political, profitable, and fiscal. The political pointers include government stability, socioeconomic conditions, investment profile, conflicts, corruption, law and order, service, religious and ethnic tensions, popular responsibility, and bureaucracy. The profitable pointers are GDP per capita, real GDP growth, affectation, financial balance, and current account balance. The fiscal pointers regard for foreign debt effects, transnational liquidity, and exchange rate stability. Even though the relationship between some indicators of health systems (similar as sanitation structure) and AMR has been assessed in the being studies, we believe there's the eventuality for a comprehensive evaluation to give richer perceptivity into the relationship. The Global Health Security Index, cooked by the Nuclear trouble Initiative, the Johns Hopkins Center for Health Security, and the Economist Impact (2022), provides a precious frame to suppose about the health system's adaptability to global pitfalls similar as AMR. The Index accounts for the capability of a given country to prevent, descry, and respond to similar pitfalls, its health system capacity, compliance with global morals, and the threat environment. Regarding climate variability, the current studies have only explored the counteraccusations of global warming, which indicates a part of the habitual climate pitfalls on AMR. It's possible to incorporate other climate variables, similar as rush, to identify the part of latent climate motorists in AMR. Likewise, an investigation of the significance of extreme climate pitfalls, such as famines, cataracts, heat and cold swells, backfires, and storms, could give a further comprehensive assessment of the counteraccusations of climate pitfalls on AMR.

3.2. Designing AMR evolution scenarios

As banded in Section 2.2, one of the main challenges in modeling the counter accusations of AMR lies in designing AMR elaboration scripts. With the limited observations of literal resistance rates, the being studies have used academic resistance rates or projected increases in unborn resistance rates. Profitable evaluations, indeed under those academic resistance rates, would still be helpful to policymakers given the complexity of AMR, lack of literal AMR surveillance, and lack of comprehensive knowledge about the evolution of AMR and query around the plethora of factors affecting it. We outline three possible approaches to improve the design of AMR elaboration scenarios. Firstly, the elaboration of conditions could be incorporated as a central step to decide mortality and morbidity estimates attributable to AMR. The existing studies substantially use mortality and morbidity rates directly attributable to precedence pathogens affecting arrange of conditions. A further grainy approach would be to model the epidemiology of conditions affected by AMR and apply AMR rates to unborn pathways of disease elaboration. The literal data on a wide array of conditions since 1990 is available from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) studies conducted by IHME. Along with the mapping of conditions to pathogens causing them and antimicrobial drug used to treat them handed in the 2019 GRAM study, dependable and more grainy scripts of the evolution of conditions and the burden of the conditions attributable to AMR could be deduced. The unborn burden attributable to AMR from conditions could be analyzed within similar scripts

using 2019 resistance rates or historical rates (where available). A range of sensitivity analyses could be conducted to support policy makers to account for the query. As both the GBD and GRAM studies also include health profitable criteria, similar as Deaths, Disability- acclimated Life Times(DALYs), Times Lived with Disability(YLDs), and Times of LifeLost(YLLs), the changes in the inflexibility of diseases could also be anatomized. Fresh weights for such considerations could be allocated within the design of scenarios. Secondly, there are extensively used scripts with recognized narratives for other global challenges affecting AMR, similar as demographic trends and climate change. The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs), which have been used to estimate climate change scenarios since the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) sixth assessment report, are defined with socioeconomic and demographic assumptions. Incorporating similar hypotheticals along with climate pathways would also help integrate the climate implications of AMR (and conditions) into the climate impact literature.

Assessing the profitable impacts of AMR alongside climate change impacts within similar modeling fabrics would also enable policy makers to compare the scale of AMR burden with climate change. Thirdly, the effect of antimicrobial consumption on the productivity of husbandry and artificial applications needs to be more understood. Indeed though the proportion of antimicrobials used among other inputs could be lower, the impact antimicrobials have on the outputs is substantial (e.g., the loss of cattle from a disease would not be preventable without antimicrobials). Similar analyses would help reliably decide the implications of exacerbating AMR on the productivity of agriculture and diligence counting on antimicrobials.

3.3. Modeling the macroeconomic implications of AMR

3.3.1. A stylized economy within the environment

The terrain mainly consists of four ecosystems air, marine ecosystems, brackish ecosystems, and soil. Shops, creatures, microorganisms, and homes are living beings in the terrain, and they interact among themselves and the enterprises. In addition to its relations with the ecosystems and living beings, enterprises also calculate on the terrain for energy. The conditioning of households and enterprises induce solid waste, backwaters, and emissions which are passed on to the environment. There are four main profitable agents in the domestic economy homes, enterprises, a government, and asset markets. The domestic frugality interacts with the foreign husbandry via an external sector. Households provide labor to the enterprises and admit stipend in return. Households calculate on enterprises for consumption and pay for goods and services using their income and means, both physical and fiscal. Homes also pay taxes to the government and admit subventions and public goods from the government. The redundant income is accrued into means via savings. When constrained for liquidity, homes could adopt from the asset markets. Firms use labor from homes, capital (debt and equity) from asset requests, and significances from the external sector when producing goods and services for households, the government, and exports. Enterprises pay wages to homes, capital rents to asset requests, and levies to the government. Enterprises could also receive investments from the external sector as foreign direct investments and invest in the asset requests or conduct foreign direct investments. The government provides public goods to households and transfers and subventions to homes and firms. It also purchases goods and a service from firms. Government expenditure is financed with levies from households and enterprises, public bonds issued to asset markets, and foreign aid from the external sector. When running a financial fat, the government could also invest in the asset markets. The asset requests combine savings from homes, investments from enterprises and the government, and foreign portfolio investments from the external sector. The asset requests could advance to homes and the government and invest in or advance to firms. The frugality is assumed to interact with the ecosystems only through homes and enterprises. Households interact with microorganisms, creatures, and plants when consuming goods and services provided by enterprises. The microorganisms, creatures, and plants also interact among themselves and with the ecosystems. Enterprises interact with the ecosystems via resource lines, emigrations, and disposal of solid waste and backwaters. The ecosystems also interact among themselves.

3.3.2. Macroeconomic shocks due to AMR within the stylized economy

Within the stylized frugality, there are six possible shocks or pathways via which AMR could impact the economy reduction in labor productivity, drop in total factor productivity of enterprises, increase in government expenditure, changes in consumption patterns, changes in ménage wealth, and changes in country and sector threat award. While the first five shocks could be illustrated in Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) models and Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, substantial characterization of fiscal requests is necessary for similar models to illustrate the changes in country threat premia. Reduction in labor productivity due to morbidity and mortality is the dominant pathway via which AMR affects the frugality. When the effectiveness of antimicrobial medicine and medical procedures relying on antimicrobial medicines reduces, the vulnerability to conditions rises, the conditions take longer to heal, and the probability of death from the conditions increases. Consequently, the volume and quality of being and potential labor force available for productive economic activities would reduce. The burden on the dependent

population groups (similar as children and the age-old) suffering from the conditions affected by AMR could further dwindle the productivity of the working- age population group. many profitable sectors would be else affected depending on how they rely on labor as an input compared to other inputs. All the studies banded in Section 2.1 have employed shocks on labor productivity, indeed though they differ in the granularity and expression approaches. Macroeconomic studies could use health economic metrics similar as DALYs, YLDs, and YLLs to formulate labor productivity shocks constantly across models, enabling model comparison to be more accessible for policymakers. Reduction in factor productivity is another important pathway for mapping AMR counteraccusations onto the economy. When the effectiveness of antimicrobials used in husbandry and artificial operations declines, the productivity of those sectors falls. The sectors that rely on those sectors would latterly be affected depending on their reliance on the directly affected sectors. A conventional approach would be to derive the productivity shocks grounded on the proportion of inputs contributed by those affected by AMR. Still, traditional approaches may underrate the broader significance of antimicrobials in the production processes and the substantial changes needed in production processes if antimicrobials aren't as effective. Therefore, productivity shocks should capture the broader part of antimicrobials in colorful affected sectors. Formulating productivity shocks at sector levels would be amenable in CGE, DSGE, and hybrid models similar as G- Cubed with sector disaggregation. For DSGE models without sectoral disaggregation, sector-specific productivity shocks could be added up to decide an frugality-wide total factor productivity shock. The financial burden of AMR is a significant yet underestimated aspect of current profitable studies. While a conveniently maintainable approach would be to assess the incremental charges borne in treating diseases affected by AMR, a comprehensive approach would also have to regard for costs for preventative measures. WHO's (2015) guidance on public action plans for AMR includes strategies, similar as strengthening national AMR surveillance, strengthening infection prevention and control, and perfecting mindfulness of the development of AMR and rational use of antimicrobials, which could be considered when going such preventive measures. The impact of consumer choices in products using antimicrobials, including antimicrobial drug and particularly food (reused or raw crops, meat, fish, and their derivations), on AMR is an arising body of exploration. Jans ⁵¹ have demonstrated consumer exposure to antimicrobials used in the food chain via both domestic and imported food. Ancillotti⁵² argue that forward looking consumers would change their food consumption preferences once educated about the consequences of AMR. The ongoing COVID- 19 epidemic is also exemplary of the changes in consumer preferences, particularly for service sectors (similar as transportation, food and beverage services, etc.), when faced with health risks and their profitable consequences, therefore, modeling the profitable impacts of changes in consumer preferences once faced with AMR risk is a helpful input for policymakers to understand the burden of AMR. Household wealth depends on their current means and the present value of anticipated unborn income flows. When faced with survival pitfalls, homes tend to increase the threat decoration of their private discount rate. Increases in the threat award could affect in substantial household wealth, mileage, and weal changes. Even though this pathway is extensively espoused in assessing the profitable consequences of diseases, it has not yet been espoused when assessing the economic effects of AMR. espousing this pathway in AMR studies could help compare literature on known conditions with AMR and observe the significance of exacerbating AMR. Asset requests, particularly fiscal requests, respond to changes in relative systemic pitfalls among countries and unsystematic pitfalls among the sectors. When faced with a global trouble that affects different countries and sectors else, investor preferences tend to change. These changes would be reflected in financial requests via the rebalancing of investments. COVID- 19 is exemplary of similar changes in financial markets. As AMR also affects specific sectors directly due to their reliance on antimicrobials (similar as husbandry) and labor(similar as services) and other sectors indirectly through product chains counting on directly affected sectors, investor preferences among sectors would change. As the methodical threat of AMR differs across countries depending on the divergent exposure of countries to factors driving AMR, investor preferences for countries would change. General equilibrium models with an illustration of fiscal requests would be suitable to demonstrate the profitable consequences of AMR due to changes in country and sector threat premia.

4. Policy implications and recommendations

This study alludes to several important policy implications. We discuss the importance of four main implications: (1) An economy-wide one-health approach to address AMR; (2) Regulation of the antimicrobial supply chain and incentivizing innovations; (3) Global cooperation to address AMR, and (4) Alleviating uncertainties for policymaking via scaling up the surveillance of AMR, encouraging research collaboration and enabling access to data on AMR and antimicrobial consumption. AMR should no longer be perceived as a challenge to the health sector or agriculture sector alone but rather as an economy-wide problem that interacts with the broader environment for two main reasons. On one hand, as illustrated in Figure 1, the consumption of antimicrobials is not limited to healthcare and agriculture but extends to the whole economy via direct or indirect dependencies. Thus, aggravating AMR will not only affect the healthcare and agriculture sector but also other economic sectors via linkages and spillovers, illustrated in Figure 3. On the other hand, the current understanding of factors affecting AMR itself demonstrates that factors beyond overuse, underuse, and misuse of antimicrobials, such as climate variability, demographic trends, governance, the quality of the

natural and built environment, and cross-border mobility also interact with AMR. Thus, adopting an economy-wide approach within a one health framework, which recognizes the interactions between the economy and the broader environment, is essential. The development of new antimicrobials is inhibited by numerous challenges, and thus preserving the existing stock of antimicrobials is essential. Regulating all the elements of the supply chain of antimicrobials is a vital part of this effort. This includes production, evaluation and market authorization, procurement and supply, consumption, and disposal, as illustrated in FAO, OIE, and WHO (2020). In the short to medium term, it is critical to obstacle the informal production of antimicrobials, prevent further expansion of informal markets (especially in developing countries), and raise awareness of antimicrobial consumption among both firms and households. It is also important to improve diagnosis and prescription standards (particularly in the healthcare sector) and regulate antimicrobial disposal throughout the economy. Incentivizing research and development and innovations to sustain the efficacy of existing antimicrobials and to explore alternatives to antimicrobials are vital in the long term. AMR is a global problem that requires global solutions built on global cooperation. As discussed in Section 1.3, there are factors affecting AMR which are beyond the control of an individual state. Given the trans boundary nature of AMR, global cooperation is essential to collectively address the issue. WHO, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), and the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE) have an active role in promoting and facilitating such cooperation. Empowering nations with limited technical and financial resources to adopt responsible regulations and collectively managing corporate interest is timely. The historical lessons from global actions towards cross-country problems such as ozone depletion, marine plastic pollution, and climate change could provide useful insights to initiate and sustain global cooperation toward AMR.

AMR creates at least two major sources of uncertainties for policy design. Firstly, the world is still learning the factors driving AMR. Secondly, the AMR rates for different antimicrobial pathogen combinations are not known for a vast majority of countries, especially Low and Low-middle Income countries. Hence, the global evolution of AMR is not yet completely understood. Given these existing uncertainties, the exact impacts of AMR on humans, the environment, and the economy as well as impact pathways cannot be fully evaluated. While we have suggested a robust pathway to model the macroeconomic consequences of AMR while navigating through these uncertainties, scaling up AMR surveillance and making data widely available are vital to produce research evidence for policymaking. Furthermore, making the commercial data related to AMR, such as those on antimicrobial consumption and sales, widely publicly available is vital to empowering ongoing.

5. Conclusion

AMR is a natural miracle where microorganisms acquire resistance to antimicrobials as part of their elaboration. Still, overuse, abuse, and underuse of antimicrobials in healthcare, husbandry (crops, beast, and monoculture), and artificial operations have aggravated AMR. In addition to antimicrobial consumption, socioeconomic, sociocultural, demographic, and environmental factors also contribute to AMR, including climate change, demographic trends similar as population aging, population growth, and migration, and plastic and metal pollution. Being profitable studies presumably underrate the burden of AMR in the absence of a comprehensive frame to incorporate the multitude of factors contributing to its evolution. In this study (1) the frugality-wide consumption of antimicrobials, (2) factors affecting AMR along with antimicrobial consumption, and (3) a stylized frugality within the broader terrain indicating the pathways via which AMR could give rise to profitable shocks. We also present a comprehensive methodology to formulate profitable shocks from AMR within DSGE or CGE models and indicate possible data sources that could be used in profitable modeling. We bandy how scripts amenable to policymakers could be developed also considering AMR relations with other global challenges. We punctuate the significance of perceptivity analyses in the profitable modeling of AMR, given the misgivings. We emphasize that modelers ameliorate the communication of results and cooperate to support policymakers in understanding and addressing the silent pandemic of AMR. We conclude the study by agitating four main policy counteraccusations arising from this exercise of developing a comprehensive macroeconomic modeling strategy for AMR. We reiterate the importance of an frugality-wide approach to managing AMR within a one- health framework that recognizes the liaison between the frugality and the broader terrain. We recognize the significance of regulating the antimicrobial force chains and incentivizing inventions and novel druthers to antimicrobials in the long term. We illustrate the trans boundary nature of AMR and call for global cooperation inactivity toward reducing not only the macroeconomic but also the holistic implications of AMR. Incipiently, we emphasize the significance of scaling up sweats to cover AMR and partake the data on antimicrobial consumption to grease research that could produce substantiation for effective policymaking.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Joginpalli B R Pharmacy College, Department of Pharmacy for all support.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

References

- [1] Rani, A., Saini, K. C., Bast, F., Varjani, S., Mehariya, S., Bhatia, S. K., Sharma, N. & Funk, C. 2021. A review on microbial products and their perspective application as antimicrobial agents. *Biomolecules*, 11, 1-28.
- [2] Davies, J. & Davies, D. 2010. Origins and evolution of antibiotic resistance. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*, 74, 417-33.
- [3] Zowalaty et al. (2016) and Grosso et al. (2012) for country case studies and Morgan et al. (2011) for a global review of non-prescription antimicrobial use.
- [4] Llor, C. & Bjerrum, L. 2014. Antimicrobial resistance: risk associated with antibiotic overuse and initiatives to reduce the problem. *Therapeutic Advances in Drug Safety*, 5, 229-41.
- [5] Schuts et al. (2016) for a review of the role of antimicrobial stewardship in hospitals in AMR and Stein et al. (2018), Ashraf & Cook (2016), Fridkin et al. (2014), and Hecker et al. (2003) for country case studies.
- [6] Nugent, C., Verlander, N. Q., Varma, S., Bradley, D. T. & Patterson, L. 2022. Examining the association between socio-demographic factors, catheter use and antibiotic prescribing in Northern Ireland primary care: a cross-sectional multilevel analysis. *Epidemiology & Infection*, 1-36.
- [7] Di, L. N., Tay, S. T., Ponnampalavanar, S. S. L. S., Pham, D. T. & Wong, L. P. 2022. Socio-Demographic Factors Associated with Antibiotics and Antibiotic Resistance Knowledge and Practices in Vietnam: A Cross-Sectional Survey. *Antibiotics*, 11, 1-11.
- [8] Alnasser, A. H. A., Al-Tawfiq, J. A., Ahmed, H. A. A., Alqithami, S. M. H., Alhaddad, Z. M. A., Rabiah, A. S. M., Albrahim, M. A. A., Al-Kalif, M. S. H., Barry, M., Tamsah, M. H., Al-Kalaif, Z. S. H., Shahadah, R. F. B., Alharbi, K. K. S. & Alnasser, A. A. H. P. k., attitude and practice towards antibiotics use and antimicrobial resistance in Saudi Arabia: A web-based cross-sectional survey. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 10(4). 2021. Public knowledge, attitude and practice towards antibiotics use and antimicrobial resistance in Saudi Arabia: A web-based cross-sectional survey. *Journal of Public Health Research*, 10, 711-18.
- [9] Jimah, T. & Ogunseitan, O. 2020. Socio-demographic characteristics of the association between knowledge of antibiotic therapy and prudent use in Ghana. *Journal of Global Health Reports*, 4, 1-10.
- [10] Chen, Y., Kirk, M. D., Stuart, R., Cheng, A. C., Pearson, S., Hayen, A., Banks, E. & Liu, B. 2019. Socio-demographic and health service factors associated with antibiotic dispensing in older Australian adults. *PLoS ONE*, 14, 1-10.
- [11] Schroder, W., Sommer, H., Gladstone, B. P., Foschi, F., Hellman, J., Evengard, B. & Tacconelli, E. 2016. Gender differences in antibiotic prescribing in the community: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 71, 1800-06.
- [12] Michael, C. A., Dominey-Howes, D. & Labbate, M., 2, 145. 2014. The antimicrobial resistance crisis: causes, consequences, and management. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 2, 145-52.
- [13] Bruinsma, N., Hutchinson, J. M., van den Bogaard, A. E., Giamarellou, H., Degener, J. & Stobberingh, E. E. 2003. Influence of population density on antibiotic resistance. *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 51, 385-90.
- [14] McKee, M., Dunnell, K., Anderson, M., Brayne, C., Charlesworth, A., Johnnton-Webber, C., Knapp, M., McGuire, A., Newton, J. N., Taylor, D. & Watt, R. G. 2021. The changing health needs of the UK population. *Health Policy*, 397, 1979-91.
- [15] Yoshikawa, T. T. 2002. Antimicrobial resistance and aging: beginning of the end of the antibiotic era? *Journal of American Geriatrics Society*, 50, 226-9.

- [16] Elisabeth, M., Maneesh, P., Katarina, S. F., Slobodan, Z. & Michael, S. 2021. Antimicrobial resistance & migrants in Sweden: Poor living conditions enforced by migration control policies as a risk factor for optimal public health management. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 9, 1-5.
- [17] Peters, A. S., Cabieses, B., Ramirez, O., Uphoff, E., Acuna, M. P., Astorga, S., Araos, R. & Munita, J. M. 2020. A systematic review on the relationship between international migration and antimicrobial resistance. *Research Square*, 1-21.
- [18] Abbas, M., Aloudat, T., Bartolomei, J., Carballo, M., Durieux-Paillard, S., Gabus, L., Jablonka, A., Jackson, Y., Kao-jaroen, K., Koch, D., Martinez, E., Mendelson, M., Petrova-Benedict, R., Tsiodras, S., Christie, D., Saam, M., Hargreaves, S. & Pittet, D. 2018. A systematic review on the relationship between international migration and antimicrobial resistance. *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control*, 7, 1-11.
- [19] Nellums, L. B., Thompson, H., Holmes, A., Castro-Sanchez, E., Otter, J. A., Norredam, M., Friedland, J. S. & Hargreaves, S. 2018. Antimicrobial resistance among migrants in Europe: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 18, 796-811.
- [20] González Zorn, B. & Escudero, J. A. 2012. Ecology of antimicrobial resistance: humans, animals, food and environment. *International Microbiology*, 15, 101-109.
- [21] Marshall, B. M., Ochieng, D. J. & Levy, S. B. 2009. Commensals: underappreciated reservoir of antibiotic resistance. *Microbe*, 45, 231-38.
- [22] Summers, A. O. 2002. Generally overlooked fundamentals of bacterial genetics and ecology. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 34, S85-92.
- [23] Pallecchi, L., Bartoloni, A., Paradisi, F. & Rossolini, G. M. 2008. Antibiotic resistance in the absence of antimicrobial use: mechanisms and implications. *Expert Review of Anti-infective Therapy*, 6, 725-32.
- [24] World Economic Forum 2020. The costs and risks of AMR water pollution. *World Economic Forum*.
- [25] Bengtsson-Palme, J., Kristiansson, E. & Larsson, D. J. 2017. Environmental factors influencing the development and spread of antibiotic resistance. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews*, 42, 68-80.
- [26] Prestinachi, F., Pezzotti, P. & Pantosti, A. 2015. Antimicrobial resistance: a global multifaceted phenomenon. *Pathogens and Global Health*, 109, 309-318.
- [27] Pham, D. N., Clark, L. & Li, M. 2021. Microplastics as hubs enriching antibiotic-resistant bacteria and pathogens in municipal activated sludge. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Letters*, 2, 1-7.
- [28] Bank, M. S. 2022. Microplastic in the environment: pattern and process, *Springer*.
- [29] Moore, R. E., Millar, C. & Moore, J. E. 2020. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and marine plastics: can food packaging litter act as a dispersal mechanism for AMR in oceanic environments? *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 150, 1-7.
- [30] Seiler, C. & Berendonik, T. U. 2012. Heavy metal driven co-selection of antibiotic resistance in soil and water bodies impacted by agriculture and aquaculture. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 3, 1-10.
- [31] Knapp, C. W., McCluskey, S. M., Singh, B. K., Campbell, C. D., Hudson, G. & Graham, D. W. 2011. Antibiotic resistance gene abundances correlate with metal and geochemical conditions in archived Scottish soils. *PLoS ONE*, 6, 1-6.
- [32] Bokhary, H., Rangesti, K. N. A., Rashid, H., Ghany, M. A. E. & Hill-Cawthorne, G. A. 2021. Travel-related antimicrobial resistance: a systematic review. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Diseases*, 6, 1-27.
- [33] Plaza-Rodriguez, C., Alt, K., Grobbel, M., Hammerl, J. A., Irrgang, A., Szabo, I., Stingl, K., Schuh, E., Wiehle, L., Pfefferkorn, B., Naumann, S., Kaesbohrer, A. & Tenhagen, B. 2021. Wildlife as sentinels of antimicrobial resistance in Germany? *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 7, 1-15.
- [34] Arnold, K. E., Williams, N. J. & Bennett, M. 2016. 'Disperse abroad in the land': the role of wildlife in the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance. *Biology Letters*, 12, 1-8.
- [35] Collignon, P., Beggs, J. J., Walsh, T. R., Gandra, S. & Laxminarayan, R. 2018. Anthropological and socioeconomic factors contributing to global antimicrobial resistance: a univariate and multivariable analysis. *Lancet Planet Health*, 2, 1-8.
- [36] Rodriguez-Verdugo, A., Lozano-Huntelman, N., Cruz-Loya, M., Savage, V. & Yeh, P. 2020. Compounding effects of climate warming and antibiotic resistance. *Science*, 23, 1-16.

- [37] Gudipati, S., Zervos, M. & Herc, E. 2020. Can the one health approach save us from the emergence and reemergence of infectious pathogens in the era of climate change: implications for antimicrobial resistance? *Antibiotics*, 9, 1-7.
- [38] Cavicchioli, R., Ripple, W. J., Timmis, K. N., Azam, F., Bakken, L. R., Baylis, M., Behrenfeld, M. J., Boetius, A., Boyd, P. W., Classen, A. T. & Crowther, T. W. 2019. Scientists' warning to humanity: microorganisms and climate change. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 17, 569-86.
- [39] Wellcome Trust. 2020. Why is it so hard to develop new antibiotics? [Online]. Wellcome Trust. Available: <https://wellcome.org/news/why-is-it-so-hard-develop-new-antibiotics> [Accessed 24 May 2021].
- [40] Ventola, C. L. 2015. The antibiotic resistance crisis: part 1: causes and threats. *Pharmacy and Therapeutics*, 40, 277-83.
- [41] McManus et al. (2002) for a review of antimicrobial use in crops and the implications on human and animal health.
- [42] O'Neil, J. C. 2016. Tackling drug-resistant infections globally: Final report and recommendations. United Kingdom.
- [43] Cecchini, M., Langer, J. & Slawomirski, L. 2015. Antimicrobial resistance in G7 countries and beyond: economic issues, policies and options for action. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.
- [44] Wozniak, T. M., Barnsbee, L., Lee, X. J. & Pacella, R. E. 2019. Using the best available data to estimate the cost of antimicrobial resistance: a systematic review. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control*, 8, 1-12.
- [45] Dadgostar, P. 2019. Antimicrobial resistance: implications and costs. *Infection and Drug Resistance*, 12, 3903-10.
- [46] Shrestha, P., Cooper, B. S., Coast, J., Oppong, R., Do Thi Thuy, N., Phodha, T., Celhay, O., Guerin, P. J., Wertheim, H. & Lubell, Y. 2018. Enumerating the economic cost of antimicrobial resistance per antibiotic consumed to inform the evaluation of interventions affecting their use. *Antimicrobial Resistance & Infection Control*, 7, 1-9.
- [47] Ahmed, S. A. A., Baris, E. & Go, D. S. 2017. Assessing the global economic and poverty effects of antimicrobial resistance. *The World Bank*.
- [48] Hillock, N. T., Merlin, T. L., Turnidge, J. & Karnon, J. 2022. Modelling the future clinical and economic burden of antimicrobial resistance: the feasibility and value of models to inform policy. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy*, 1-8.
- [49] Linton, A. H. 1977. Animal to man transmission of Enterobacteriaceae. *Royal Society of Health Journal*, 97, 115-18.
- [50] McEntee (2000) for a compendium of antimicrobials used in industrial applications.
- [51] Jans, C., Sarno, E., Collineau, L., Meile, L., Stark, K. D. C. & Stephan, R. 2018. Consumer exposure to antimicrobial resistant bacteria from food at Swiss retail level. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9, 1-19.
- [52] Ancillotti, M., Nilsson, E., Nordvall, A. & Oljans, E. 2022. The status quo problem and the role of consumers against antimicrobial resistance. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 6, 1-5.

Author's Short biography

Raju Darla having 14+ years of experience in various fields in advanced scientific research and development. During this time, built up research and 35+ Publications both nationally and internationally, and 15+ Awards and Honor's and participated 60+Conferences and completed 65+ additional course certificates through online platforms, leading to substantial contribution in leadership, teaching and management.